

The Dharmalakshana Buddhist Institute 佛教法相學會, Hong Kong

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Entry tags: Chinese Buddhist Traditions, Yogacara Buddhism, Faxiang school (faxiang zong 法相宗), Religious Group, Consciousness-only School, Chinese Buddhism, Buddhist Traditions, Cantonese, Language, Religious Practice, Scholastic Buddhism, Chinese Religion

The Dharmalakshana Buddhist Institute is a Hong Kong Buddhist organization chiefly found by the famous Buddhist layman and scholar Lo Shi-hin 羅時憲 (1914 – 1993) in 1965. The aims of the Institute are to promote Yogācāra thought, a section of Mahāyāna Buddhism that it emphasizes the importance of philosophical argument in the process of reaching Buddhahood, and to improve the quality of the Buddhism in Chinese society through the learning of Yogācāra thought. There was, in fact, a unique background of the foundation of the Institute. Since the early 20th century, the Buddhism in China, the thoughts of Pure Land 淨土 and Chan 禪 in particular, was severely criticized as superstitious, conservative and passive, as related thoughts were believed to ignore such society-relevant issues as poverty and inequality, but only paid attention to the obtainment of a quiet and pure mind. As a result, the Buddhist in China in that time was considered ignorant to the world and it made the future of the Buddhism there pessimistic. In order to prevent the Buddhism in China from further deteriorating, individual Buddhist figures such as Taixu 太虛 (1890 – 1947) and Ouyang Jian 歐陽漸 (1871 – 1943) tried to promote the thought of Yogācāra, as the thought is regarded as highly scientific, argumentative and even earthly, and through the learning of it, the situation of the Buddhism in China could be eventually improved. As the political conditions got worse since 1930s, however, the suggestion of Taixu and Ouyang Jian failed, and it is widely held that the movement of promoting Yogācāra thought in China came to an end in the late 1940s. Beyond all expectations, Lo Shi-hin, a disciple of Taixu and an admirer of Ouyang Jian, left mainland China and arrived Hong Kong in 1949, and recommended Yogācāra thought in the British colony. From 1954 to 1965, Lo Shi-hin taught Ch'eng Wei-Shih Lun 成唯識論, the Yogācāra classic translated and edited by Xuanzang 玄奘 (602 – 664) and Kuījī 窺基 (632 – 682), in a local Buddhist society, and the teaching became a landmark of a continuation of the wills of Taixu and Ouyang Jian. After the completion of the teaching, Lo Shi-hin, together with other 13 disciples including Wei Tat (韋達), Lee Yun Sang (李潤生) and Huo Tao Hui (霍韜晦), found the Dharmalakshana Buddhist Institute, aiming to promote Yogācāra thought in a more systematic way. Since then, the Institute, on the one hand, keeps teaching the Yogācāra thought especially those as inherited by Xuanzang, while, on the other hand, helps improve the arguments of such traditional Chinese Buddhist thoughts as Pure Land, Tiantai 天台, Huayan 華嚴 and Chan. The Dharmalakshana Buddhist Institute is probably the only Buddhist organization in Chinese society who actively promotes the thought of Yogācāra now, and most of the Yogācāra works from the line of Xuanzang have been discussed by the members of the Institute. Many of their interpretations have also been published. To a large extent, the movement of promoting Yogācāra thought as happened in the early Republican China has not ended but is ongoing in Hong Kong. This important intellectual movement is certainly worth our further attention.

Date Range: 1965 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Hong Kong

Region tags: Hong Kong

A British colony from 1842 to 30 June 1997, and now a part of the People's Republic of China.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: 趙敬邦，〈唯識在香港的傳承〉，《中國文哲研究通訊》第24卷，第2期(10 / 2014) : 37-48。
- Source 2: Eyal Aviv, Differentiating the Pearl From the Fish Eye: Ouyang Jingwu (1871 – 1943) and the Revival of Scholastic Buddhism (Unpublished PhD Thesis: Harvard University, 2008).
- Source 3: Wei Tat (韋達) trans., Ch'eng Wei-Shih Lun: Doctrine of Mere-Consciousness (Hong Kong: The Ch'eng Wei-shih Lun Publication Committee, 1973).
- Source 1: John Makeham ed., Transforming Consciousness: Yogācāra Thought in Modern China (New York: Oxford University Press, 2014).
- Source 2: 鄧家宙，〈香港佛教史〉(香港：中華書局，2015年)。

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <http://www.dhalbi.org/>

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: [file:///C:/Users/kpchi/Downloads/wzfy_trad%20\(1\).pdf](file:///C:/Users/kpchi/Downloads/wzfy_trad%20(1).pdf)
- Source 1 Description: A masterpiece in Yogācāra thought written by Lo Shi-hin

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– No

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: There are cooperations between the Dharmalakshana Buddhist Institute and other Buddhist societies in Hong Kong. These cooperations are mainly providing different kinds of Buddhist courses in various levels, aiming at improving the quality of the Buddhism in the society as a whole. Unlike its predecessors in the early Republican China who considered Yogācāra thought superior in Buddhism, the Dharmalakshana Buddhist Institute views the relationship between Yogācāra and other Buddhist thoughts in a more equal and friendly way, regarding them partners of collaboration rather than rivals of competition.

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Notes: The Institute is an independent Buddhist organization, which, on the one hand, does not belong to a larger religious organization, while, on the other hand, does not intervene its member to join other religious activities.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Notes: There are regular activities run by the Institute, mainly scholarly courses about Buddhist thought, open for participation. Participants are usually attracted by the high quality of the courses and except this no active recruitment of new members is observed.

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Notes: Membership is always open. Members can join or leave the Institute freely.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 300

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (one of many small religious groups in sample region)

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Obviously, Lo Shi-hin, the founder of the Institute, is the spiritual leader.

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– No

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– No

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

Notes: .

↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:

– No

↳ A leader's retinue or ministers chooses the new leader:

– No

↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:

– Yes

Notes: The leaders are chosen via votes by all of the directors of the Institute.

↳ A political leader chooses the leader:

– No

↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:

– No

↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:

– No

↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection

process:

– No

Notes: The criteria of selection are mainly based on the academic level and leadership of the candidate.

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

Notes: Since the leader is simply an ordinary person, he / she is considered fallible and everyone can criticize the leader in principle.

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:

– Yes

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– No

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: Introduction to Yogācāra Buddhism 唯識方隅, a work written by Lo Shi-hin, is highly respected in the Institute. Although the title of the book is called 'introduction', it is not an introductory but a profound work about Yogācāra thought. Members of the Institute, to different extent, are affected by the views of the book.

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they oral:

– No

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– Yes

Notes: As a scholarly work, Lo Shi-hin's Introduction to Yogācāra Buddhism is always open for discussion and the content of it is certainly revisable if mistakes are to be found.

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– No

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– No

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– No

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– No

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– No

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: As a Buddhist organization which promotes Yogācāra thought, the Institute stresses the importance and even existence of Ālaya-vijñāna, a concept similar to a substratum consciousness. As Paul Williams argues, such substratum consciousness ‘is personal, individual, continually changing and yet serving to give a degree of personal identity and to explain why it is that certain karmic results pertain to this particular individual.’ In short, this substratum consciousness helps explain both the actuality and potentiality of a sentient being, and even those of the world. And it is believed to be the true self of a sentient being beyond the body. For more discussion, see Paul Williams, *Mahāyāna Buddhism: The Doctrinal Foundations* (Oxon and New York: Routledge, 2009), pp. 97-100.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: Ālaya-vijñāna is regarded as a repository for the ‘seeds’ or bīja of a sentient being. Since the conditions of one’s ‘seeds’ are affected by his / her / its own karma, in this sense, seeds are considered the results of one’s karma. On the other hand, it is also the cause of one’s future live. The above probably explains that the functions of ālaya-vijñāna are much more than that of our bodies, though the bodies are also developed from our ālaya-vijñānas.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– No

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: Since Yogācāra is a part of Buddhism and the Dharmalakshana Buddhist Institute is a Buddhist organization promoting Yogācāra thought, the Institute also believes in afterlife as other Buddhist sects do.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

Notes: In Buddhism, the status of reincarnation is totally decided by one's own deeds. In principle, one could be a human or any other beings next live, depending on one's conduct this life and even previous lives. The Institute obviously follows this rule of Buddhism.

↳ In a human form:

– Yes

↳ In animal/plant form:

– Yes

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s):

– Yes

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage. etc.):

– I don't know

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma):

– Yes

↳ Other form of reincarnation in this world:

– I don't know

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– No

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: If Buddha and bodhisattva are considered 'supernatural beings', the answer is yes. However, in Buddhism, Buddha and bodhisattva are transformed from ordinary people. In this sense, the supernatural power that a 'supernatural being' may enjoy is developed by training.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– No

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Human in the past, in theory, should have rebirthed through the process of reincarnation. In this regard, previously human spirits could be considered to exist in the human spirits in this live, though most of the humans this live may not remember the human spirits in the past.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: In the Buddhist tradition, there are always non-human divine beings, which plays as the guardians of Buddhas and other bodhisattvas.

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– I don't know

Notes: It seems that seeing or feeling of such non-human divine beings are mostly decided by one's own karma. There is no clear or simple answer to this question.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– I don't know

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: If considering that both Buddha and bodhisattva are 'divine' and they are transformed from ordinary people, then it is correct to say that mixed human-divine beings are present.

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be seen:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

Notes: Like the situation of non-human divine beings, seeing or feeling of mixed human-divine beings are seemingly decided by one's own karma. And there is no simple answer to this question.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– I don't know

Notes: According to Buddhism, Abhijñā, a kind of direct knowledge or supernatural power is to be obtained through mediation, and this ability has no limits. It is believed that Buddhas, bodhisattvas and even some monks have such ability.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– I don't know

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– I don't know

↳ Mixed human-divine beings know your basic character (personal

essence):

– I don't know

↳ Mixed human-divine beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– I don't know

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have other knowledge of the human world:

– I don't know

↳ These mixed human-divine beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Notes: In Buddhism, the result of a human is ultimately decided by his or her own conduct. The human-divine beings is only a kind of assist.

↳ These mixed human-divine beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit negative emotion:

– No

↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess hunger:

– I don't know

↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– I don't know

↳ Mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living:

– Yes

Notes: If Buddhas and bodhisattvas are considered human-divine beings here, it is argued in Buddhism that they always try to communicate with other sentient beings by all means in order to help the latter reach Buddhahood.

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

- ↳ In dreams:
 - Yes
- ↳ In trance possession:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Through divination practices:
 - Yes
- ↳ Only through religious specialists:
 - No
- ↳ Only through monarch:
 - No
- ↳ Other form of communication with living:
 - Yes [specify]: In Mahāyāna Buddhism, Buddhas and bodhisattvas do not reject any possible ways to communicate with others as long as the ways are helpful.
- ↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:
 - No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The Yogācāra Bodhisattva Precepts 瑜伽菩薩戒本, which emphasizes the importance of feasibility and flexibility of a precept as recorded in the Yogācārabhūmi-Śāstra 瑜伽師地論, is highly regarded in the Institute, though following the precepts is not compulsory for its members. For details about the content of the Precepts, see Ester Bianchi, 'Yogācāra Bodhisattva Precepts in Twentieth Century China: Reevaluating Rules and Commitments in the Light of Modernity', in Ester Bianchi and Daniela Campo ed., "Take the Vinaya as Your Master": Monastic Discipline and Practices in Modern Chinese Buddhism (Leiden: Brill, 2023), pp. 193-229.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: As the promotion of Yogācāra thought is always the aim of the Institute, virtues as stressed in Yogācāra thought are, therefore, considered important from the view of the Institute.

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):

– No

↳ Courage (generic):

– Yes

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– I don't know

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Yes

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– I don't know

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– Yes

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– I don't know

↳ Cooperation:

– Yes

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– I don't know

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– Yes

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– Yes

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:

– Yes

↳ Strength (physical):

– No

↳ Power / status / nobility:

– No

↳ Humility / modesty:

– I don't know

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:

– I don't know

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:

– Yes

↳ Optimism / hope:

– I don't know

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:

– I don't know

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:

– No

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:

– Yes

↳ Wisdom / understanding:

– Yes

↳ Discernment / intelligence:

– I don't know

Beauty / attractiveness:

– I don't know

Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– I don't know

Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– I don't know

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: Lectures, Chan (Zen) practices and other Buddhist ceremonies are provided by the Institute, and members are encouraged to particulate. However, the participation is voluntary but not compulsory. In this sense, sacrifice of time is not a must but up to the decision of individuals.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:
I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A band

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through

an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– No

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– No

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No